

Emergence of Neologisms in the Context of Social Media and How It Affects Students' Socio-pragmatic Communication: Foundation for the Development of a Portfolio Guide of Social Media Registers to be Utilized in Select SHS Subjects

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Abstract

This research was conducted to investigate how multiple neologisms utilized in the context of social media can affect students' socio-pragmatic communication. Since technology has made communication easier and more effective, language has been tremendously influenced. The way individuals connect, communicate, and socialize has changed as technology has advanced. These changes and developments have resulted in the formation of a new lexicon of words and phrases that many of us use to communicate effectively in order to cope with the changing nature of social communication and language culture. The researcher discovered that these variations in vocabulary acquisition have a major impact on students' verbal competence. Many of these new words have already been incorporated into dictionaries. But, despite their widespread use, the majority of students were reported to be unaware of the semantics, word types, and word formation mechanisms of the chosen neologisms. Thus, the need for a portfolio guide featuring neologisms was developed, with the goal of assisting students in deciphering the meanings and identifying the word types and word formation processes that these words undergo. The researcher utilized a descriptive study design. According to Bernard (2012), descriptive research is used to "describe" a situation, subject, behavior, or phenomenon. Participants were chosen for this study based on convenience and purposive sampling: those who were online and easily accessible, as well as those who had prior knowledge of neologisms. As revealed in the fgd, interviews and surveys conducted, neologism usage can affect students' socio-pragmatic communication-social use of language, especially when the meanings are obscure. As a result, students' language and vocabulary learning suffered, resulting in poor communicative performance.

Keywords: Neologisms, Socio-pragmatics, Word-formation Processes, Communicative Performance, Social Media, Social Media Register

Introduction

This study was conducted in the hope that the emergence of neologisms or millennial terms encountered in the context of contemporary technological breakthroughs in internet-based communication, where these words surface, can be explored, defined, and classified. There are thousands of newly created terms being used on various social media sites that are already widespread and embraced by today's generation, which the researcher felt compelled to investigate and analyze, as well as their corresponding effects on English vocabulary and socio-pragmatic communication. Linguist David Crystal famously expressed that in the twenty-first century, the internet will be the trend that would have the largest impact on the English language.

The occurrences of neologisms and how they are being used and understood socially in various social media platforms are the focus of this study. Neologisms were only seen and used once an author wrote a book, novel, sonnets, poems, tragedies, or any other sort of literature in the previous several decades. Shakespeare was one of his generation's most well-known authors, who not only made significant contributions to the disciplines of play and literature, but also influenced how linguistics was employed in the past. His contributions to vocabulary extension have had a significant impact on English language learning, teaching, and communication.

Millennials, often known as digital natives, are already being dubbed "modern-day Shakespeare" because various terms have already been made, coined, and invented and are frequently used on social media. The rise and widespread use of various social media platforms has had a big impact on how words are made and used, as it is the primary platform for these newly developed terms to surface and propagate throughout various sites. Words that are unfamiliar to us but are widely used by internet users because they are popularly trending, artistically produced, and many have used them in their online social communication. As a result, neologism in social media have emerged, and the researcher is certain that the emergence of neologisms that are widely used across various social media platforms have been affected by students'

pragmatic language or the way they use language socially. This study was conducted to look for several neologisms (new terminology) used on various social media platforms, how they mean in that context and how it can affect one's social-pragmatic competence. Furthermore, the morphological processes and word types were also determined.

Literature Review

Vygotsky, as mentioned in the study *Vygotskian Vocabulary Development in the Secondary Classroom* believed that students construct new knowledge, concepts, and skills through interacting with other members of their culture. This cultural interaction allows the students to learn the symbols that will later form the basis of their thought processes. Vygotsky used the term "sign" to represent these culture-based mental symbols (e.g., words, numbers, or images).

Vygotsky's sociocultural theory views human development as a socially mediated process in which children acquire their cultural values, beliefs, and problem-solving strategies through collaborative dialogues with more knowledgeable members of society. His theories stress the fundamental role of social interaction in the development of cognition (as mentioned in an article entitled *Lev Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory* by McLeod, 2020), as he believed strongly that community plays a central role in the process of "making meaning."

Conversation exchanges between students who are engaged on social media develop into intrapersonal dialogues, which are then transformed into vocabulary and speech acquisition. This means that modern technology has an impact on how people communicate online and how they alter their language to comprehend and be understood by the social milieu in which they find themselves. In some instances, new words are created. In some instances, new words are being formed for the way language being used nowadays are affected by how online society dictates it. This is referred to as "social meaning negotiation." As a result, how language is used socially shapes the online collaborative sharing of words, phrases, and thoughts, giving rise to social media registers or neologisms.

Neologisms present new words that differ from already existing words in English

vocabulary. As regards to creating new words, different types of morphological processes occur. Peoples' creativity to communicate faster has accelerated the transformation of language rhythm and words. Thus, neologisms keep appearing and expanding the English vocabulary and it is to be claimed that a better and clearer understanding of them guides learners to use the English language in all kinds of ways, gain necessary information, and improve their communication ability (Shahlee & Mustaffa 2019: 1-2).

Statement of the Problem

Specifically, the proponent of this research sought to answer the following:

1. What are the multiple neologisms used in the context of social media?
2. What do these Neologisms mean?
3. How are these social media neologisms be categorized in terms of:
 - 3.1 word types?
 - 3.2 morphological word-formation processes?
4. How can these neologisms affect students' socio-pragmatic communication?
5. What supplementary material featuring social media registers may be developed?

Research Methodology

a. Sampling

Convenience sampling is defined as a method adopted by researchers where they collect market research data from a conveniently available pool of respondents. It is the most commonly used sampling technique as it's incredibly prompt, uncomplicated, and economical. On the other hand, as to purposive sampling and how the researcher utilized it, two processes were applied. To begin, by the time that these students were already known to most likely post neologisms, the researcher would purposively visit their social media accounts and examine every post they had shared.

b. Data Collection

In conducting the study, the researcher utilized the qualitative approach in order to discuss and illustrate how word formations were being processed and which word types they would fall under. The study was initiated by choosing timely issues related to the study

of the Vocabulary Acquisition and Formation. The researcher used famous social networking sites because it is a popular medium where students would be mostly active. The researcher used the research tools of non-participant observation, themes and coding, and documentary analysis.

Documentary analysis was also utilized in this study. It is a systematic procedure for reviewing or evaluating documents—both printed and electronic material. The documents that were analyzed in this study are the different posts of students in social networking sites. Like other analytical methods in qualitative research, document analysis requires that data be examined and interpreted in order to elicit meaning, gain understanding, and develop empirical knowledge (Corbin & Strauss, 2008). All the posts from sites were analyzed and classified into different types of morphological word formation processes.

Furthermore, to analyze effectively how these collected means would mean socially, themes and codes were conceptualized and created. Themes are features of participants' accounts characterizing particular perceptions and/or experiences that the researcher sees as relevant to the research question. Coding is the process of identifying themes in accounts and attaching labels (codes) to index them. Also, according to Gibbs (2007) in qualitative research, coding is how you define what the data you are analyzing are about.

Discussion of Results and Recommendations Neologisms: Meanings and Classifications

Neologisms	Definition	Word Type	Word Formation Process
Unfriend	To remove someone's name from your list of friends on a social networking site	Verb	Affixation (fixing prefix 'un-' to 'friend')
Unlike	To click an icon on Facebook to show you no longer like an item you previously liked (www.facebook.com)	Verb	Semantic extension
Vlog	A blog that produces regular video content on a particular theme on the internet (www.blogspot.com)	Noun	Blending (video + blog)
Vodcast	A downloadable video program from a social network website	Noun	Blending (Video + Podcast)

Webinar	Meetings, trainings or presentations conducted live on the internet (www.livinginternet.com)	Noun	Blending (Web + seminar)
Hakdog	A Filipino word use to sabotage or make a person angry	Millennial Expression	Compounding Fusion of Filipino and English word (Ha *What + Dog)
Lol	Laughing out loud	Millennial Expression	Acronym
Izzaaprank	Filipino term/expression for "It's a prank"	Millennial Expression	Coinage
Marites	Modern day chismosa. Filipino term to describe a person who gossips and spreads rumors	Adjective	Name Association
Krazzy	Filipino term for Crazy	Adjective	Change on spelling Coinage
Periodt.	The end of a discussion or to emphasize a point.	Millennial Expression	Change on spelling
Whatever	Whatever	Millennial Expression	Change on spelling Coinage
Chillax	To relax	Verb	Blending (Chill + Relax)
BRB	Be right back	Millennial Expression	Acronym
Lods	Filipino expression for Idol	Noun	Coinage
GG	Good game	Millennial Expression	Acronym
G!	Game!	Millennial Expression	Acronym
Dancerist	Tiktok derived word means good dancer or someone who can dance	Adjective, Noun	Affixation (+ist)
Singerist	Tiktok derived word means good singer or someone who can sing	Adjective, Noun	Affixation (+ist)
I kennat!	I can't!	Millennial Expression	Change of spelling
Dunno	Don't know	Millennial Expression	Change of spelling and Blending (Don't + Know)

Blending, compounding, affixation, semantic extension, and coinage were some of the word-formation types that have been identified in the data, and some of the word classes they belong to were nouns, verbs, and adjectives are among those they belong to.

Among the neologisms used in this study, blending is the type of word formation that is most frequently encountered. A similar study conducted by Cook and Stevenson (2010) found that blends accounted for approximately 44 percent of the neologisms examined, which is comparable to the current findings.

The word "noun" appears to be the most frequently encountered word-class in the data. This is consistent with Stekauer's concept of onomasiology. Because words are invented to give names to already existing objects and concepts, it is only natural that the majority of neologisms are nouns. The above analysis also revealed that neologisms can only be classified as belonging to the open class of English words, which includes nouns, verbs, and adjectives—the three-word classes that were identified among the neologisms in this study—and not as belonging to any other class of words. They

are typically capable of assimilating new words into their class, in contrast to grammatical words, which only rarely incorporate neologisms into their class.

Neologisms: Its Impact on Students' Socio-Pragmatic Communication

As revealed in an interview and fgd conducted as regards how these newly created vocabularies affect the social-pragmatic communication of students, most of them mentioned that using these neologisms to express themselves socially-through social media gave them a sense of belongingness and the feeling of being unique and creative as well. They emphasized that these neologisms that surfaced online were socially embraced and socially utilized. Though most of the words that surfaced online were unknown to them, they found it very trendy that they would research the meaning so that they could utilize the words they had just acquired and encountered online.

Social media does, in fact, play an important part in language acquisition. One noteworthy finding regarding the favorable influence of social media on language learners' confidence, attitude, and motivation was that their confidence, attitude, and motivation improved dramatically. Learners claimed that using social media platforms has instilled a more positive attitude toward learning English since these sites provide elements that allow users to improve their language skills (Kabilan et al., 2010). Learners are exposed to a wide range of texts via social media, particularly Facebook and Tiktok. Learners will not only be able to examine and read various written writings shared by other users, but they will also be able to keep up with global current events via Twitter and Facebook. Learners will get an enormous number of new phrases and words without having to read many books or go to the library, according to Khan, Ayaz Khan, and Khan (2016), and their general language skills will be strengthened by the increase in vocabulary.

For the most part, students who participated in an interview and fgd about the impact of these newly created vocabularies on social-pragmatic communication said that using them in social media gave them a sense of belonging as well as a sense of being unique and creative. They pointed out that these new words and phrases that appeared online were

accepted and used by the general public. Despite the fact that many of the words they encountered online were new to them, they found it fashionable to research their meanings so that they could put them to use.

Several neologisms were collected and delineated in the analysis. The observation method of data collection was used to gather social media neologisms from both primary and secondary sources; and the qualitative modes of inquiry were adapted. The primary sources were mostly social networking websites; while the secondary sources were published works in which some neologisms were documented and defined. The qualitative mode of analysis involved a definition of each neologism, revealing its meaning, word-class, word-formation process, and its impact on how students use language/vocabularies socially.

Dissemination and Advocacy Plans

Results and findings of the study would be presented through informal SLAC sessions. Discussion on the utilization of material and its implementation would be facilitated and considered. Analysis on the language needs of the students would also be carried out to properly utilize the material derived from this study. Students would be exposed on the different neologisms that have propagated online and through the utilization of the material created through this study, they will be educated on the processes and classifications of these newly coined terms which can be properly used by the students. Assessment of the material would be administered to evaluate its effectiveness and relevance to the vocabulary knowledge of the students.

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